

European Policy
Innovation Council

From Draghi to DNA

Building Europe's Competitiveness Through Connectivity

November 2025

Published by the European Policy Innovation Council (EPIC)

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EPIC is an independent Brussels-based think tank dedicated to connecting research with policy. Its mission is to strengthen Europe's competitiveness through forward-looking, evidence-based dialogue between academics, policymakers, and industry leaders. The Draghi Observatory & Implementation Index, launched by EPIC in September 2025, follows up on the implementation of the Report on the Future of European Competitiveness, tracking reforms and identifying new ideas to sustain Europe's growth model. Our Index has been widely covered by global media, including the Financial Times, The Economist, and Politico, and has quickly become the reference point for evaluating the progress of reforms across the EU.

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Page layout: Altais

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Executive Summary

Europe's competitiveness challenge has entered a decisive phase. The *Report on the Future of European Competitiveness* by Mario Draghi identifies connectivity as one of the structural foundations of Europe's economic renewal. Telecommunications and digital networks underpin the capacity of every sector to innovate, scale and compete. Yet Europe's telecom sector continues to operate below potential: investment levels remain insufficient, market fragmentation persists, and regulatory complexity slows the deployment of next-generation networks.

This report examines how the forthcoming **Digital Networks Act (DNA)** can help close these gaps. Using 20 telecom-relevant measures extracted from EPIC'S Draghi Observatory & Implementation Index, this study assesses their political and institutional feasibility in the context of the DNA. Each measure is classified as **likely, unlikely, highly unlikely or unclear**, based on Commission signals, Member State positions and legal constraints.

Feasibility of Draghi's Telecom Recommendations (20 measures)

Likelihood	Count	Percentage
Likely	7	35%
Unlikely	7	35%
Highly unlikely	2	10%
Unclear	4	20%

Only 35% of Draghi's telecom recommendations are likely to be reflected in the DNA. Half of the measures face low feasibility or political resistance, while one-fifth remain uncertain.

A six-pillar analysis reveals a highly uneven feasibility landscape:

1. **Security and technological sovereignty** is the only pillar with strong political momentum 100% likely.
2. **Spectrum policy, investment-driven regulation**, and regulatory simplification display mixed or uncertain prospects.
3. **Fair contribution, same service/same rules, and market scale/consolidation** face the strongest political constraints, with most measures unlikely or highly unlikely to be included.

These findings highlight that Europe's challenge is not conceptual alignment with Draghi's recommendations, which is often high, but the ability to translate these recommendations into **operational mechanisms** within the limits of political feasibility, Member State prerogatives and institutional realities.

The DNA remains Europe's first significant test of legislative delivery under the Draghi agenda. If it advances the feasible elements (notably security, resilience, technological sovereignty, and simplified deployment) it can provide the foundations for a more competitive and innovation-ready telecom environment. But without progress on spectrum predictability, regulatory proportionality, and market scale, the structural investment gap will persist.

Only 35% of Draghi's telecom recommendations show a realistic path to delivery – security and technological sovereignty stand out as the only pillar with clear momentum.”

This report represents the **before phase** of the Draghi Observatory methodology: identifying what the DNA should deliver to be consistent with the Draghi agenda. Once the Commission publishes the DNA proposal, the **Draghi Implementation Points (DIPs)** will be assigned, generating a measurable scorecard of legislative delivery. These results will feed into the 2026 Draghi Implementation Index, establishing a comparative baseline for evaluating the performance of European institutions across policy domains.

1. Introduction – Competitiveness through Connectivity

The Report on the Future of European Competitiveness by Mario Draghi provides a stark assessment of Europe's economic position. It describes a continent with world-class ambitions but limited capacity to deliver them. Productivity growth has stalled, investment levels remain below global competitors, and structural rigidities prevent the scale needed to drive innovation. While Europe continues to lead in regulatory sophistication, it lags in the ability to convert policy ambition into market competitiveness.

Connectivity stands at the heart of this challenge. Telecommunications and digital networks are no longer an ordinary sector of the internal market; they form the backbone of Europe's capacity to compete. The quality and integration of these networks determine how fast European industries innovate, how efficiently public administrations operate, and how securely citizens and businesses can rely on digital services. Connectivity underpins the productivity of every sector, from manufacturing and energy to research and logistics, and thus defines the continent's overall economic resilience.

Yet the telecom sector itself remains under structural pressure. Over the past decade, revenues have stagnated while investment costs have risen. Capital returns are below the cost of capital, and market fragmentation continues to erode efficiency. Europe still counts more than one hundred mobile operators, compared with a handful in the United States or China. This fragmented structure prevents economies of scale, constrains innovation, and slows the rollout of advanced technologies such as fibre, 5G, and emerging 6G networks.

The *Draghi Report* identifies these weaknesses as systemic and calls for a comprehensive policy reset. It argues that Europe must move away from fragmented, prescriptive, and nationally focused regulation and toward a single, investment-driven telecom market. The recommended reforms include harmonised spectrum policy, greater scope for consolidation, and the principle of *same service, same rules* to ensure a fair competitive environment. Security and sustainability are also presented as core components of competitiveness, not as external constraints.

These recommendations form the analytical foundation for this study, which examines how the forthcoming Digital Networks Act (DNA) can operationalise Draghi's vision. The report analyses the current state of implementation across the sector, identifies the main policy gaps, and outlines what the DNA should include to close them.

The next chapter presents the methodology used to assess implementation, drawing on the Draghi Observatory's data and analytical framework. It explains how legislative progress is tracked through the coding of measures, implementation categories, and the assignment of Draghi Implementation Points (DIPs): the measurable policy levers that will later serve to evaluate the effectiveness of the legislative act.

2. Methodology

This analysis is based on the Draghi Observatory, a research framework that monitors how European policies reflect and implement the recommendations of the *Report on the Future of European Competitiveness* prepared by Mario Draghi in 2024. The Observatory compiles and evaluates policy measures across multiple sectors (digital, industrial, financial, and technological) to assess the level of implementation of the 383 measures included in the Draghi Report.

Each measure in the Observatory dataset is coded according to its implementation status: *implemented*, *in progress*, *partially implemented*, or *not implemented*. The dataset also records the time horizon (short, medium, or long term), the responsible Directorate-General, and a qualitative summary of political and regulatory developments. This approach allows for both quantitative measurement and qualitative interpretation, offering a structured view of progress or lack thereof.

The first audit of the Draghi Observatory, published in September 2025, established a baseline for assessing implementation across all policy domains. It found that only 11,2 percent of Draghi's overall recommendations had been implemented. In the field of digitalisation and advanced tech, which includes telecommunications, connectivity, and frontier technology, the distribution was similar to the general index with 10,6 percent of measures implemented.

The Overall Scoreboard

Category	% of Total	Number of Measures
Implemented	11.2%	43
Partially Implemented	20.1%	77
In Progress	46.0%	176
Not Implemented	22.7%	87
Total	100%	383

Strict Index (Implemented only): 11.2%
 Partial Index (Implemented + Partially Implemented): 31.4%

Results by Sector

Sector	Implem.	Part. Impl.	In Progr.	Not Impl.	Total	Strict (%)	Strict+Partial (%)
Automotive	0 (0.0%)	11 (45.8%)	6 (25.0%)	7 (29.2%)	24	0.0%	45.8%
Clean tech	1 (2.6%)	12 (30.8%)	16 (41.0%)	10 (25.6%)	39	2.6%	33.3%
CRM	19 (33.3%)	2 (3.5%)	21 (36.8%)	15 (26.3%)	57	33.3%	36.8%
Defence	0 (0.0%)	5 (35.7%)	5 (35.7%)	4 (28.6%)	14	0.0%	35.7%
Digitalisation & tech	5 (10.6%)	6 (12.8%)	25 (53.2%)	11 (23.4%)	47	10.6%	23.4%
Energy	0 (0.0%)	13 (15.7%)	55 (66.3%)	15 (18.1%)	83	0.0%	15.7%
Ells	7 (16.7%)	10 (23.8%)	16 (38.1%)	9 (21.4%)	42	16.7%	40.5%
Pharma	0 (0.0%)	5 (27.8%)	10 (55.6%)	3 (16.7%)	18	0.0%	27.8%
Space	0 (0.0%)	5 (27.8%)	8 (44.4%)	5 (27.8%)	18	0.0%	27.8%
Transport	11 (26.8%)	8 (19.5%)	14 (34.1%)	8 (19.5%)	41	26.8%	46.3%
Total	43 (11.2%)	77 (20.1%)	176 (46.0%)	87 (22.7%)	383	11.2%	31.4%

A further distinction is necessary within the implementation categories used by the Draghi Observatory. **The category "in progress" identifies measures that are currently under political or technical discussion, but it does not indicate movement toward adoption or convergence. A measure may be marked "in progress" because it is being debated, even if the direction of travel is uncertain or unlikely to lead to implementation.**

For the purpose of this report, the analysis introduces an additional layer by distinguishing between measures that are **likely, unlikely, highly unlikely** or **unclear** in terms of future implementation. This refinement draws on evidence from ongoing political discussions surrounding the DNA, including Member State positions, Commission signals, and institutional feasibility. It provides a more meaningful interpretation of policy momentum and reflects the real prospects for delivering the recommendations of the Draghi Report.

The Draghi Implementation Points (DIPs)

Building on this dataset, the Draghi Implementation Points (DIPs) framework translates Draghi's recommendations into measurable indicators of legislative delivery. Each DIP reflects the extent to which a specific policy measure has been incorporated into a Commission proposal. Taken together, the DIPs provide a standardised method for assessing how far a legislative initiative, such as the forthcoming DNA, advances the objectives set out in the Draghi Report.

The "Before and After" Mechanism

The Observatory applies a two-phase analytical process.

1. **Before phase:** assesses upcoming or proposed legislation to identify what each initiative should include to be consistent with the Draghi Report.
2. **After phase:** to be conducted once the legislation is tabled, evaluates how much of the Draghi agenda has been incorporated, assigns DIPs accordingly, and suggests amendments to improve alignment.

This report represents the **before phase** for the DNA. It assesses the state of progress across existing policy measures and sets expectations for what the Act should deliver. The synthesis phase, which will assign implementation points and measure legislative delivery, will take place following the publication of the DNA.

Analytical Process

The research combines quantitative scoring with qualitative synthesis through the following steps:

- **Data extraction** from the Draghi Observatory's Digitalisation and Advanced Tech dataset, identifying the 20 measures most relevant to telecommunications.
- **Coding** of each measure using the 4 implementation categories: implemented, partially implemented, in progress, and not implemented.
- **Clustering** of measures into 6 pillars: Scale, Regulation, Single Market, Spectrum, Same Service/Same Rules, and Security/Sustainability.
- **Alignment** of each measure and pillar to the scope of the forthcoming DNA and to the Directorates-General responsible.
- **Assignment of Draghi Implementation Points (DIPs)** once the European Commission publishes the DNA proposal, allowing a full "after phase" assessment of legislative delivery with a scorecard.

Through this structured process, the report ensures both **credibility** and **replicability**. It provides a transparent framework for future analysis under the Draghi Observatory, enabling the tracking of legislative performance and the comparison of implementation progress overall and across the European Commission's Directorates-General.

The following chapter summarises Draghi's main recommendations for the telecom and digital sector, forming the reference point for the subsequent implementation analysis.

3. Draghi's Telecom and Digital Agenda

Telecommunications and connectivity are central to Europe's economic renewal. The *Draghi Report* views digital infrastructure as both a precondition for innovation and a sector that urgently requires reform. Connectivity enables the transformation of industries, the deployment of advanced technologies, and the resilience of supply chains. Yet, as the report notes, the European telecom sector operates below its potential because it remains fragmented, overregulated, and underinvested. The recommendations summarised below establish the framework for evaluating how the DNA can close these structural gaps.

Pillar	Policy Intent (Draghi Report)
1. Scale and Market Structure	Create the conditions for stronger, more efficient European telecom operators through consolidation and cross-border integration. The report calls for merger policy to reflect innovation and investment criteria—not just short-term consumer price effects—and to enable scale comparable to global peers. Operators interpret this as support for a reassessment of EU competition rules and merger control practice, allowing investment-driven consolidation within a reformed regulatory framework.
2. Regulation	Shift from prescriptive ex ante rules at national level to a lighter, ex post enforcement regime focused on preventing abuse of dominance. The goal is to free up investment in fibre, 5G, and future infrastructure while maintaining competition safeguards. Operators see this as recognition that the current regulatory burden, designed for the early liberalisation period, has become counterproductive in a mature and capital-intensive market.
3. Single Market Integration	Reduce national fragmentation by harmonising telecom regulation, enabling cross-border services, and promoting passporting for business-to-business connectivity. The Draghi Report emphasises that the lack of a unified telecom market undermines efficiency and scale. Industry interprets this as a call to establish consistent EU-level rules, removing duplicative authorisations and diverging national obligations that raise costs and slow innovation.
4. Spectrum Policy	Harmonise spectrum allocation, extend licence durations, and reduce auction fragmentation. Draghi highlights the need to double spectrum licence terms, align frequency release schedules, and limit the use of caps or reservations to cases of market dominance. This approach would encourage investment, predictability, and innovation in next-generation networks, from 5G to 6G.
5. Level Playing Field ("Same Service, Same Rules")	Introduce a horizontal regulatory principle ensuring that all providers of equivalent services—telecom operators and digital platforms alike—are subject to comparable obligations. Draghi explicitly endorses the idea of a "same service, same rules" framework to remove regulatory arbitrage between sectors. Operators view this as essential to fair competition and as an incentive for long-term network investment.
6. Security and Sustainability	Strengthen the security, resilience, and sustainability of networks as integral components of competitiveness. Draghi calls for reduced dependence on non-EU suppliers, coordinated cybersecurity frameworks, and support for European technological capabilities. On sustainability, he advocates balancing decarbonisation targets with competitiveness and innovation, recognising the enabling role of digital technologies in energy efficiency and climate transition.

These six pillars form the reference structure for the analysis that follows. The next chapter evaluates the degree to which these recommendations have been implemented across the European Union, using data from the Draghi Observatory to establish the baseline for alignment with the upcoming DNA.

4. Implementation Snapshot

This section assesses the state of implementation of the Draghi Report’s recommendations in the field of telecommunications and digital infrastructure. It builds directly on the methodology outlined earlier and uses data from the Draghi Observatory Dataset on Digitalisation and Advanced Technologies (September 2025). The data provide a structured view of where the European Union stands in translating Draghi’s competitiveness agenda into telecom policy.

The analysis focuses on the twenty measures most directly related to telecoms and connectivity — those that fall within the scope of the forthcoming Digital Networks Act (DNA). Each measure is categorised according to its current implementation status: Implemented, In Progress, Partially Implemented, or Not Implemented. **It should be noted that several measures marked as ‘In Progress’ reflect ongoing political or technical discussions, which may not yet lead to legislative or regulatory change.** The table below summarises these findings:

Theme	Measure	Status	Comment
Fair Share	Encourage negotiated data traffic cost-sharing with arbitration mechanisms	In Progress (unlikely)	Active Commission consultations; proposal may enter DNA, but no binding framework yet.
Scale and Market Structure	Increase the weight of innovation and investment in merger control	In Progress (unlikely)	EC consultation launched in May 2025; innovation increasingly cited in merger cases but no formal rule change.
Scale and Market Structure	Define telecom markets at the EU level to facilitate cross-border integration	Not Implemented	No EU-wide market definitions; remedies remain national and price-based.
Scale and Market Structure	Enable ex post merger monitoring and remedial tools for post-clearance competition issues	Not Implemented	Still limited to ex ante enforcement; post-merger monitoring not codified.
Spectrum Policy	Harmonise 6G band releases across Member States	In Progress (unclear)	6G roadmap and RSPG coordination improving, but auctions remain nationally controlled.
Spectrum Policy	Double licence durations and enable secondary trading	Not Implemented	Some Member States offer 20-year terms, but no EU-wide mandate for extended or tradable licences.

Spectrum Policy	Limit spectrum reservations and caps to dominance cases	In Progress (unclear)	National discretion unchanged; discussions ongoing, no legal provisions adopted.
Spectrum Policy	Allocate additional WiFi-dedicated bands to preserve unlicensed spectrum	In Progress (unclear)	6 GHz band harmonised; debate ongoing over upper 6 GHz; no new WiFi bands formally allocated.
Security and Resilience	Harmonise cybersecurity rules and strengthen ENISA cooperation	Partially Implemented	Strong progress via NIS2, DORA, and CRA; lawful interception remains nationally fragmented.
Network Transition	Phase out copper and 2G/3G networks with social protection measures	In Progress (unclear)	Several Member States have national plans, but no EU-wide deadlines or protection schemes.
Regulatory Reform	Reduce national ex ante regulation; move toward ex post enforcement focused on abuse of dominance	In Progress (unlikely)	Policy discussions on regulatory adjustments continue, but full structural change is unlikely, given the market conditions do not support such a shift at this stage.
Regulatory Reform	Introduce "same rules for same services" across telecom and digital platforms	In Progress (unlikely)	Acknowledged in DNA consultation; partial alignment via DMA/DSA but no comprehensive equivalence regime yet.
Regulatory Simplification	Deregulate new investments (fibre, 5G, IoT) while preserving retail competition	In Progress (unclear)	Gigabit Infrastructure Act streamlines rollout; competition oversight still applies.
Single Market Integration	Introduce EU "passporting" for B2B telecom services	Not Implemented	No cross-border authorisation framework; concept excluded from DNA scope.
Security and Industrial Policy	Prioritise EU trusted vendors in future spectrum tenders	Partially Implemented	National restrictions on high-risk vendors; no EU-wide preference or mandate.
Security and Industrial Policy	Enforce compliance with 5G Toolbox and trusted vendor sourcing	Partially Implemented	Implementation uneven across Member States; no binding EU deadlines.
Innovation and R&D	Support virtualisation and 6G research via IPCEIs and joint undertakings	Partially Implemented	SNS JU and Horizon Europe fund next-gen projects; commercial adoption still limited.
Standardisation	Mandate EU-level body to coordinate cross-platform standards	In Progress (likely)	Coordination improving through AIOI and ETSI; no central authority established.
Standardisation	Adopt agreed standards across Member States to ensure interoperability	In Progress (unclear)	Progress under European Standardisation Strategy, but adoption remains fragmented.
Competitiveness Infrastructure	Support trusted, EU-compliant hosting and cloud infrastructure expansion	In Progress (likely)	Gaia-X and AI Factories progressing; no formal certification for "compliant" hosting yet.

Synthesis and Analysis

The data reveal a mixed picture. Out of twenty telecom and connectivity measures, none have been fully implemented, while more than half remain in progress. The overall direction of EU policy broadly aligns with Draghi's recommendations, but tangible delivery is slow and fragmented. While most measures are classified as in progress, many remain in the discussion phase with no guarantee of follow-up or implementation.

Market scale shows the least progress. Despite repeated recognition of the need for consolidation and cross-border integration, competition policy continues to operate on national definitions, and merger reviews still prioritise short-term consumer welfare. Without a single market framework for telecoms, investment efficiency remains limited.

Regulatory reform is advancing conceptually, with multiple consultations under way, but the practical shift from ex ante to ex post enforcement remains unfulfilled. There is currently limited political or practical feasibility for major adjustments to the existing regulatory framework. Resistance from smaller operators and national regulators underscores how deeply entrenched the current regime is.

Spectrum policy is partially converging through coordination efforts for 6G rollout, yet auctions and licence regimes remain national. Draghi's call to double licence durations and create tradable spectrum rights has not been acted upon, leaving Europe behind global peers in regulatory predictability.

The **level playing field** debate—"same service, same rules"—is one of the few areas of visible momentum. The principle is now mainstream in policy discussions and reflected in the DNA consultation. Likewise, the **fair-share** question, that is how large platforms contribute to network costs, is recognised as a legitimate issue, though consensus on its resolution is elusive.

Progress in **security and sustainability** is more tangible. EU cybersecurity legislation (NIS2, DORA, CRA) has strengthened resilience and coordination, and national restrictions on high-risk vendors are tightening supply-chain security. However, these advances remain uneven and primarily national, while sustainability goals are addressed through R&D rather than direct telecom regulation.

In sum, implementation across the telecom domain is partial and uneven. Political commitment to reform is strong, but operational follow-through lags. The Draghi Observatory's 2025 audit confirms this pattern: among the 47 measures assessed across digitalisation and advanced technologies, only 10.6 percent are implemented, 12.8 percent partially implemented, 53.2

percent in progress, and 23.4 percent not implemented. Telecom measures fall squarely within this distribution.

The above data establish the empirical baseline for the next phase of the analysis. They show where progress has been made and where gaps persist between the Draghi agenda and EU policy reality.

5. Draghi – DNA Alignment

The DNA is expected to serve as the main legislative vehicle for implementing the recommendations of the *Report on the Future of European Competitiveness* in the digital and connectivity sectors. The Act represents a shift from strategic planning to delivery, testing whether the European Union can transform the Draghi agenda into tangible results.

The following table examines how the DNA should align with the key recommendations of the Draghi Report. It identifies how the forthcoming legislation can implement Draghi's vision on the aforementioned six pillars.

Table 2. DNA – Draghi Alignment Matrix

Pillar	Objective	Current Status	What the DNA Should Do	Responsible DG
1. Spectrum Predictability and Scale	Provide a harmonised, long-term spectrum framework to reduce regulatory uncertainty and encourage infrastructure deployment.	Coordination improving under RSPG, but auctions, licence durations, and renewals remain national.	Establish minimum EU standards for licence duration, renewal, and trading to create a predictable investment environment.	DG CNECT
2. Same Service, Same Rules	Ensure functional equivalence across telecom and digital sectors to restore a level playing field.	Principle endorsed under DMA/DSA but not applied to telecom legislation.	Integrate a horizontal clause in the DNA requiring regulatory symmetry for functionally equivalent services.	DG CNECT
3. Fair and Proportionate Contribution Framework	Encourage balanced cost-sharing between network operators and large traffic generators while safeguarding net neutrality.	Commission consultation ongoing; no policy proposal or mechanism yet.	Include a reference framework for negotiated cost-sharing or arbitration under the DNA, consistent with EU competition principles.	DG CNECT / DG COMP

4. Consolidation and Cross-Border Scale	Enable EU-wide operators through reformed merger assessment criteria and cross-border authorisation.	Discussions advancing in merger review; not part of DNA's legal base.	Include interpretative guidance in the DNA encouraging NRAs and competition authorities to consider innovation and investment outcomes in market assessments.	DG COMP / DG CNECT
5. Investment-Driven Regulation	Shift from prescriptive ex ante obligations toward ex post, innovation-focused oversight to stimulate long-term investment.	Reform acknowledged in policy debates; still nationally fragmented and procedural.	Allow for a gradual rebalancing of market oversight within the DNA, streamlining analysis obligations where justified by investment needs.	DG CNECT / DG COMP
6. Security and Technological Sovereignty	Strengthen Europe's network resilience and reduce dependency on non-EU suppliers.	Frameworks (NIS2, DORA, CRA, 5G Toolbox) operational but unevenly enforced.	Align DNA provisions with NIS2 implementation, integrate trusted vendor principles, and link with EU industrial programmes (STEP, IPCEI).	DG CNECT / DG GROW

Alignment Implications

The alignment mapping shows how the DNA could be broadly consistent with Draghi's competitiveness logic with a complete scope and enforceability. The Act should recognise the right principles, i.e., investment, scale, resilience, and innovation, but also turn them into binding mechanisms.

A balanced approach to **regulatory adaptation** is essential to encourage investment while safeguarding competition. Without clear legal provisions, national fragmentation will persist, deterring cross-border investment. Progress on regulatory simplification will depend on Member State consensus and practical feasibility within the existing framework.

Spectrum predictability remains the largest structural gap. The DNA should aim to improve predictability by promoting more consistent licence and renewal practices. Coordination through the RSPG is a positive step but cannot substitute for a unified European framework.

Market scale and consolidation are still blocked by outdated competition rules. While the DNA cannot directly amend merger law, it can influence implementation by mandating that NRAs and competition authorities consider long-term innovation and investment outcomes.

The **fair-share** and **level-playing-field** debates are the most politically sensitive. The DNA should create the conditions for transparent, negotiated mechanisms that balance the financial burden of network investment while ensuring parity between operators and digital platforms.

Finally, **security and technological sovereignty** must be embedded at the heart of the DNA. Integrating trusted vendor principles and aligning with industrial programmes such as STEP and IPCEIs would ensure that competitiveness and resilience advance together.

Box 1. Risks if Key Elements Are Omitted

- Continued fragmentation and uncertainty in telecom regulation.
- Ongoing underinvestment in digital infrastructure.
- Delayed 6G rollout and industrial digitalisation.
- Sustained dependency on non-EU technology suppliers.
- Loss of competitiveness and strategic autonomy for the EU.

Box 2. Opportunities if Key Elements Are Included

- A predictable, investment-friendly framework for telecoms.
- Greater economies of scale and improved cost efficiency.
- Faster deployment of next-generation networks.
- Fairer competition between operators and platforms.
- Stronger resilience, security, and technological independence.

The DNA is Europe's first legislative opportunity to implement the Draghi competitiveness agenda in full. If it integrates the six pillars outlined above, it can transform Europe's telecom sector into a driver of competitiveness and innovation. The DNA will then stand not only as a policy reform, but as a **proof of concept** for how Europe can deliver the Draghi agenda across all sectors by linking strategic ambition with measurable legislative delivery.

6. Implementation Scorecard (Preliminary)

The Draghi Implementation Points (DIPs) translate the analysis of the preceding chapters into a set of actionable policy levers. They summarise how the Digital Networks Act (DNA) should operationalise the competitiveness priorities identified by Mario Draghi and form the measurable bridge between strategic ambition and legislative design.

Each DIP reflects a concrete policy dimension where the DNA can close existing gaps between the Draghi Report's recommendations and the current state of EU telecom policy. Together, these points form a structured framework for evaluating implementation – one that can later be replicated across other sectors as part of the Draghi Implementation Index in 2026.

Table 3. Anticipating Draghi's Telecom Recommendations to the DNA

DNA Policy Lever	Current Gap / Assessment	Likelihood
1. Establish "same service, same rules" principle across telecom and digital sectors	Horizontal equivalence clause under discussion; references to DMA/DSA interoperability rules. The concept is recognised, but no defined mechanism exists to operationalise equivalence across all services.	Unlikely
2. Facilitate consolidation and scale through revised merger assessment criteria	Indirect link: the Commission is exploring investment and innovation metrics in merger policy, but this remains outside the DNA's legal scope.	Unlikely
3. Create EU-level market definitions for cross-border services	No proposal foreseen to harmonise authorisations or redefine telecom markets at the EU level.	Highly Unlikely
4. Harmonise spectrum allocation and auction procedures	Common roadmap for 6G under DNA and RSPG coordination improves planning but leaves Member States in control of auctions and licence durations.	Unlikely
5. Extend licence duration and enable secondary trading	Discussed under the "predictable investment framework" concept, but not explicitly included in the consultation; remains a national competence.	Highly Unlikely
6. Limit spectrum reservations and caps to dominance cases	Mentioned under spectrum efficiency and competition safeguards, but without binding provisions or enforcement criteria.	Unclear
7. Promote cross-border spectrum coordination for pan-EU coverage	The DNA is expected to strengthen Commission guidance on 6G releases, but coordination remains procedural, not legal.	Unclear
8. Incentivise investment through fair contribution models ("fair share")	Open consultation ongoing on large traffic generators and cost allocation. No consensus reached; the DNA may include only guiding principles.	Unlikely

<p>9. Shift from ex ante to more flexible oversight to support investment</p>	<p>Discussions continue on how to make regulatory obligations more proportionate. These debates remain at an early stage, and Member States show limited appetite for structural change. The DNA may explore selective adjustments, but no major shift away from ex ante regulation is currently anticipated.</p>	<p> Unlikely</p>
<p>10. Introduce simplified permitting for network rollout</p>	<p>Likely continuity with the Gigabit Infrastructure Act (GIA). Alignment strong — GIA principles expected to be extended.</p>	<p> Likely</p>
<p>11. Encourage voluntary consolidation through EU-level investment funds</p>	<p>Potential link to the Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP), but no telecom-specific financing tools proposed.</p>	<p> Unlikely</p>
<p>12. Ensure interoperability and cross-border service continuity</p>	<p>Alignment with Digital Decade targets; no binding mechanism to guarantee interoperability across networks.</p>	<p> Unclear</p>
<p>13. Secure networks and diversify suppliers (“trusted vendor” principle)</p>	<p>DNA expected to reference the 5G Toolbox and cybersecurity frameworks; consistent with NIS2 and CRA.</p>	<p> Likely</p>
<p>14. Coordinate cybersecurity oversight and enforcement</p>	<p>Integration of NIS2 and DORA procedures foreseen. Strong conceptual alignment, though implementation will depend on Member State enforcement.</p>	<p> Likely</p>
<p>15. Promote European technological sovereignty (6G, edge, cloud)</p>	<p>DNA aligns with the Chips Act and Digital Decade objectives but lacks direct industrial policy instruments.</p>	<p> Likely</p>
<p>16. Embed sustainability in network design and investment criteria</p>	<p>Environmental performance reporting foreseen for operators, but incentives limited to disclosure obligations.</p>	<p> Unclear</p>
<p>17. Support SMEs in adopting advanced digital services</p>	<p>Addressed indirectly via coverage and B2B connectivity; no specific SME-focused provisions.</p>	<p> Unlikely</p>
<p>18. Improve enforcement of competition and consumer protection rules</p>	<p>DNA expected to streamline coordination between NRAs and the Commission. Strong alignment in principle, pending governance details.</p>	<p> Likely</p>
<p>19. Create a monitoring mechanism for investment and deployment targets</p>	<p>Annual review foreseen under Digital Decade governance; design of performance indicators still pending.</p>	<p> Likely</p>
<p>20. Strengthen single market governance through greater EC coordination</p>	<p>DNA expected to expand Commission powers over NRAs and cross-border cases. Aligned with Draghi's call for stronger central oversight.</p>	<p> Likely</p>

Assessment of Implementation Prospects

This feasibility mapping provides a forward-looking assessment of how the forthcoming Digital Networks Act (DNA) is likely to reflect the telecommunications recommendations of the Draghi Report. Only a limited number of Draghi's measures currently have a realistic prospect of being incorporated into the Act. Areas related to security, cybersecurity coordination, technological sovereignty, network resilience, market oversight and simplified permitting show comparatively strong feasibility. These priorities benefit from broad political support and continuity with existing EU frameworks such as NIS2, the Cyber Resilience Act and the Gigabit Infrastructure Act.

Likelihood of Implementation (20 Measures)

Likelihood	Count	Percentage
Likely	7	35%
Unlikely	7	35%
Highly unlikely	2	10%
Unclear	4	20%

By contrast, measures involving structural regulatory reform, spectrum harmonisation, cross-border market integration, fair-share mechanisms and competition policy face significant institutional constraints. Member States remain cautious about centralisation and reluctant to adjust established regulatory competences, making major changes in these areas unlikely in the current legislative cycle. Several proposals, such as EU-level market definitions or harmonised licence durations, are effectively outside the scope of the DNA.

A substantial number of recommendations fall into the unclear category. These are areas where discussions are active but outcomes remain uncertain, either because Member States are divided or because the Commission has not yet clarified the ambition of the Act. Examples include spectrum coordination, interoperability and sustainability-related measures.

Taken together, the feasibility assessment shows that Europe's challenge is not recognising the importance of Draghi's recommendations but translating them into operational mechanisms within the limits of political and institutional feasibility. Based on consultations to date, **only 35% of Draghi's telecom recommendations are likely to be reflected in the DNA**, while the **Security & Sovereignty pillar stands out as the only component with clear and consistent political momentum**.

The DNA will need to evolve from declaratory ambition to practical implementation if it is to contribute meaningfully to Europe's competitiveness. Addressing the feasibility gaps identified in this analysis would mark a shift toward execution, transforming Draghi's recommendations from a strategic blueprint into an operational framework for European renewal.

The Draghi Observatory will continue to monitor legislative and political developments throughout the negotiation process. Once the DNA proposal is published, the Observatory will assign Draghi Implementation Points (DIPs) and evaluate delivery across Directorates-General as part of the 2026 Draghi Implementation Index, establishing a comparative baseline for tracking the EU's progress on the competitiveness agenda.

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